

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Electrodeposited p-Cu₂O Films – Role of Redox-Active Compounds Under Photoelectrochemical Operation Revisited

Michael Neumann-Spallart¹ | Dharini Bhagat² | Šárka Paušová¹ | Josef Krýsa¹ | Indrajit Mukhopadhyay²

¹Department of Inorganic Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Prague, Czech Republic | ²Department of Solar Energy, Pandit Deendayal Energy University, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India

Correspondence: Josef Krýsa (josef.krýsa@vscht.cz)

Received: 2 December 2024 | **Revised:** 4 February 2025 | **Accepted:** 10 February 2025

Funding: “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call “Excellent Research”.

Keywords: cuprous oxide | photoelectrochemical stability | p-type semiconductor

ABSTRACT

The p-type semiconducting copper oxides CuO and Cu₂O are of interest for the conversion of solar energy due to their medium-wide bandgap and the position of their conduction band, allowing for reductive processes in junctions with electrolytes under irradiation. In this work, on Cu₂O, the efficiency of several such processes in competition with self-reduction is critically reviewed and experimentally studied. Up to 2000 nm thick films were obtained via potentiostatic electrodeposition on fluorine-doped tin oxide on glass from alkaline solutions of CuSO₄ using lactic acid as a complexant. The films consisted of a dense arrangement of crystallites as seen by scanning electron microscopy and were of phase pure Cu₂O as shown by X-ray diffraction (XRD). The films were specular, with an absorption coefficient of 50,000 cm⁻¹ at 480 nm and a direct bandgap of 2.5 eV. In junctions with aqueous electrolytes, the material was found to be p-type. Under electrical bias, cathodic and photocathodic currents passed and increased dramatically when reducible redox compounds were added. The influence of various redox couples (O₂, H₂O₂, and methylviologen [MV, 1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium]) and their concentration in the electrolyte on the stability of the electrodes was studied. Long-time experiments showed that to avoid degradation of the electrodes, the use of oxygen-saturated solutions was mandatory when no other redox couple was added. H₂O₂-containing electrolytes gave rise to constant photocurrents and no alteration of the electrodes was found by XRD. MV yielded cathodic photocurrents. Reoxidation of its reduced form by dissolved oxygen was necessary in order to hinder dimerization or further reduction to MV⁰ and association of the latter to MV⁰_n, producing a whitish layer on top of the electrodes which led to their inactivation.

1 | Introduction

p-type semiconductor/liquid junctions can be used for electrosynthetic reductions under visible (solar) light illumination if they have appropriate band gaps and band positions. Cu-based oxides may qualify for this task. In this context, CuO and Cu₂O have been

investigated, especially in view of the photo-assisted reduction of water to hydrogen. Photocorrosion remained to be a problem, especially for CuO [1–3].

Cuprous oxide (Cu₂O, cuprite) is a suitable photocathodic material due to its optical properties and non-toxic nature.

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Bandgap energies (E_g) between 2.0 and 2.6 eV have been reported [4], a spread which is due to various reasons such as deposition method, electrode potential in electrodeposition, oxygen pressure in physical deposition, etc. For a bandgap of 2.1 eV, Cu_2O can theoretically convert 18% of the photons of the solar light to charge carriers, and for a bandgap of 2.5 eV, 9%, based on published solar spectra [5]. Cu_2O is a p-type semiconductor due to the presence of Cu vacancies. It dissolves below pH 4 [6] and has low stability against reduction to Cu upon operation in a photoelectrochemical cell in the absence of appropriate electron acceptors [7]. This reaction may be hindered in various ways like surface modification using co-catalyst deposition [8], deposition of blocking layers and construction of stratified electrodes including catalysts [7, 8] or tuning of crystal facets [9]. As to band positions, especially the position of the conduction band (CB) is of interest, as the potential of photogenerated charge carriers (electrons) at this level would lead to envisaged charge transfer reactions (reduction) of solutes in the case of a junction with an electrolyte. If the potential of the CB is calculated based on measurements of the flatband potential (fb) (e.g. [3]), it would also depend on E_g , which can vary considerably (see above), but for all combinations of published values of bandgap and fb, a CB potential which is sufficiently negative for reduction of protons to hydrogen was found. This is the reason for the strong interest in this material.

The purpose of this work is to see whether CB processes with various electron acceptors on unmodified Cu_2O electrodes can be found and whether such reactions can proceed with prominent photocurrent and electrode stability. Besides electron acceptors such as dissolved oxygen and hydrogen peroxide, methylviologen (MV, 1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium) as an acceptor is reinvestigated and critically reviewed. Electrodes (thin layers) were synthesized via electrodeposition from an aqueous bath using lactic acid as a complexant on conductive fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) glass. Emphasis was given to several issues not reported or fully explained previously, for example: i) detailed X-ray diffraction (XRD) study of Cu_2O stability under air and oxygen bubbling, ii) optical properties of Cu_2O films, iii) extension of the range of oxygen concentrations to an even higher concentration by using a 50:50 water:ethanol mixture, iv) discussion of the influence of various oxygen concentrations including literature reference and our own previous measurements and v) dependence of dark currents and photocurrents on the concentration of various electron scavengers, formation of products of MV reduction.

2 | Experimental

Cu_2O layers were prepared by electrodeposition from an aqueous CuSO_4 /lactate bath held at 60°C on FTO substrates (F:SnO₂/glass, TEC-7, Sigma Aldrich), following a description [10]. The bath composition was CuSO_4 0.4 M, lactic acid (2-hydroxypropanoic acid) 3 M, and NaOH 3.8 M.

The phase composition of the layers was determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) with an X'Pert³ MRD (Malvern Panalytical) diffractometer. Thickness was measured by profilometry (Dektak XT, Bruker) or by optical interference using a fibre optic spectrometer (Ocean Optics) and the program Nanocalc. Surface

morphology was investigated using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) model Hitachi S-4800, and UV-VIS studies used a UV-2600i UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu).

Measurements of photoelectrochemical properties were carried out using a three-electrode cell with an Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode and a Pt counter electrode. A W-Hal lamp or a solar simulator with an irradiance of 100 mW/cm² (AM 1.5) was used as a light source. Phosphate buffer pH 8 and Na₂SO₄ (0.1 M in water or in ethanol/water [50/50]) were used as electrolytes. Methyl viologen ("MV", 1,1'-dimethyl-1,1'-dihydro-4,4'-bipyridine) dichloride hydrate was obtained from Sigma Aldrich and used without further purification.

Nitrogen and oxygen were used for gas saturation of the electrolytes. Four different concentrations of oxygen in aqueous electrolytes were used. When the electrochemical cell was purged with nitrogen, the O₂ concentration was only 0.004 mM, as previously tested [11]. The oxygen concentration for air-saturated solutions was experimentally determined to be 0.24 mM [11]. In oxygen-saturated solutions, the nominal oxygen concentration was 1.4 mM according to [12]. Doubling of the saturation oxygen concentration was expected in an ethanol-water mixture of 50:50 using solubility data from the literature [13].

PAR, Voltalab PGZ100 (Radiometer), VersaSTAT4 (Ametek) potentiostats, and Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference and Pt counter electrodes were used. Electrochemical cells were equipped with fused silica windows and had provision for gas bubbling and stirring.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Electrochemical Deposition of Films on FTO

Electrodeposition followed a method described [10]. A polarization curve of an FTO electrode in a CuSO_4 /lactate bath under an optimized deposition temperature of 60°C is shown in Figure S1a. Electrodeposition on FTO was carried out at -0.3 V vs. Ag/AgCl (Figure S1b) and led to the formation of orange layers. The deposition time was 2000 to 3000 s. Integrated charges (Q) up to 3 C were drawn in typical runs on FTO substrates. Films of thicknesses (d) up to 2000 nm were deposited on FTO. Typical examples of thickness measurements are shown in Table 1. From Q , the thickness was estimated using $\rho = 6 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and assuming a Faradaic efficiency of 1. Alternatively, the thickness was measured by profilometry (Dektak) of a scratch, or by optical interference spectroscopy (Nanocalc). Good agreement of the measurements using the different methods was obtained.

3.2 | Physical Characterisation

Electrodeposited films had a smooth and specular appearance. From transmission (t) and reflection (r) spectra (Figure 1), the absorption coefficient (α) was calculated using $\ln((1-r)/t) = \alpha d$. The absorption coefficient reached 50000 cm⁻¹ at 480 nm. A bandgap of 2.5 eV was obtained from a Tauc plot (Figure 1b)

TABLE 1 | Thickness (d/nm) of typical electrodeposited layers.

Q of deposition (C)	d by Q	d by profilometry	d by optical interference
1.05	737	850	714
2.19	1757	1800	—

FIGURE 1 | Optical properties of an electrodeposited film. (a) Measured transmission (t) and reflection (r) spectra, calculated sum of reflection and transmission spectrum ($r+t$) and absorption coefficient α ; (b) Tauc plot assuming a direct electronic transition (Tauc function = $[\alpha h\nu]^2$).

assuming a direct electronic transition. This rather high value seems to be typical for electrodeposited Cu_2O as reported by Brown and Choi [14]. Structural reasons, as also observed as a function of deposition potential (see below) may be responsible for that. A high band gap of 2.35 eV was also found for Cu_2O synthesized by thermal reduction of CuO [15].

The presence of Cu_2O was confirmed by XRD (Figure 2a). Side products (tenorite, Cu) were not found in the diffractograms. SnO_2 Cassiterite peaks were from the substrate (FTO). The films showed phase pure cuprite. Two deposition potentials were compared (-0.3 V and -0.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl) and it was found that the ratio of the intensities of the two diffraction lines with (200) and (111) directions changed. Films deposited at -0.3 V had preferential (200) orientation in contrast to films obtained at less negative potentials (Figure S2), which had peak ratios

FIGURE 2 | (a) X-ray diffraction (XRD) of a 900 nm thick film on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO). The reference Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) lines [16, 17] show the peak positions of cuprite, tenorite, copper, and cassiterite (S, substrate); (b) XRD of a 500 nm thick film after annealing in vacuum at 400°C , 30 min.

for the (111) and (200) planes as given by powder diffraction data [16].

Some films were post-annealed in a vacuum. These films did not show any improvement as to crystallinity, nor as to photoelectrochemical response, and did not show the presence of Cu (Figure 2b).

SEM studies of the surface (Figure 3a) showed a dense arrangement of crystallites and some crystal faces of pyramidal shape (111). The presence of crystallites indicates kinetically controlled growth. Slabs of (200) oriented platelets may be distinguished at higher magnification (Figure 3b) as building blocks of the pyramids.

FIGURE 3 | Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) pictures of a typical 1800 nm thick film electrodeposited at -0.3 V versus Ag/AgCl. (a) magnification 10,000 \times and (b) magnification 20,000 \times .

3.3 | Photoelectrochemical Properties

3.3.1 | Influence of pH and Oxygen Concentration

On p-Cu₂O, electrochemical reductions can be carried out. In the following, photoelectrochemical (PEC) properties of Cu₂O electrodes were determined. Cathodic photocurrents appeared under illumination (Figure 4a).

The inset in Figure 4b shows that the electrodes behaved in the expected way for oxide electrodes, with the open circuit potential under light shifting by -59 mV/pH, corresponding to an identical shift of the band potentials. Therefore, for comparison, the j - E curves were replotted with reference to the hypothetical reversible hydrogen electrode, rHE. The Cu₂O electrode showed almost twice as high photocurrents at pH 8. Reasons for this may be differences in the efficiency of the electron transfer reaction,

FIGURE 4 | Current density—potential behaviour of a Cu_2O electrode (area 1 cm^2) under simulated AM1.5 irradiation (chopped) in oxygen-saturated solutions: (a) in $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ (pH 6) and (b) comparison of j - E behaviour at pH 6 and pH 8 (buffered) replotted against the reversible hydrogen electrode (E vs. rHE = E vs. Ag/AgCl + $0.059 \text{ pH} + E^0_{\text{Ag/AgCl}}$). Inset: open circuit potentials (OCP) in the dark and under illumination for pH 6 and pH 8.

experiencing a different surface at the two pH values, considering the isoelectric point (IEP) of Cu_2O lying at $\text{pH} < 6$ [18]. The photocurrent onset (0.7 V vs. rHE) may give a rough estimation of the fb ($0.75 \pm 0.05 \text{ V}$ vs. rHE was reported by Paracchino et al. [3]). Estimating a difference of 0.1 V between fb and valence band and using a bandgap of 2.5 eV (see above), the CB would lie at -1.7 V versus NHE, i.e. negative enough to afford all reduction reactions studied in this investigation, and also proton reduction to hydrogen.

The reactions responsible for the photocurrents can be i) reduction of cuprous oxide to Cu or ii) reduction of electroactive species dissolved in the electrolyte. The O_2 content of the electrolyte ($\text{pH} \sim 6$) had a big impact on cathodic photocurrents on Cu_2O , as already noticed at pH 8 for Cu_2O electrodes obtained by thermal reduction of CuO [15]. Figure 5 shows the long-time (4 h) current behaviour of photocurrents at -0.5 V versus Ag/AgCl in an oxygen-saturated solution (1.4 mM). The photocurrents were quite stable but relatively large dark currents were produced which increased in the long run. Schöppel and Gerischer [19] invoked interband states for oxygen reduction in the dark. In general, as Memming [20] pointed out, in the case of p-type

FIGURE 5 | Influence of oxygen concentration in the electrolyte (pH 6). Electrolyte $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$, N_2 - nitrogen saturated, O_2 - oxygen saturated, $E = -0.5 \text{ V}$ versus Ag/AgCl.

electrodes, the (dark) current limitation under reverse bias is not very efficient as local high fields at dislocations and kinks lead to the thermal activation of minority carriers.

In contrast, in the absence of dissolved oxygen ($[\text{O}_2] = 0.004 \text{ mM}$), relatively small photo- and dark currents passed. This was due to the absence of reducible species in the solution. The only possible reaction under light and in the dark was reduction of the electrode itself. In an electrolyte with a medium oxygen concentration (air-saturated solution), the dark currents were higher, and the photocurrents were significantly higher (results not shown). This has already been noticed by de Jongh et al. [21]. However, the oxygen concentration for air-saturated solutions (0.24 mM) was not sufficient to suppress auto-reduction of the electrodes completely, as already after 2000 s of polarization (total charge passed -0.8 C/cm^2) the unwanted presence of Cu was seen in the XRD (Figure 6, uppermost trace and inset of a slow scan XRD). In oxygen-saturated electrolytes as tested in a long run under polarisation and illumination (-1.1 C/cm^2 passed), no alteration of the XRD was noticed (Figure 6, middle trace). Tests were continued for up to 4 h (reaching a charge of -2.5 C/cm^2 , Figure 5).

In order to increase the oxygen concentration even more, an ethanol/water mixture (50:50) was used. Doubling of the saturation oxygen concentration was expected [13]. However, there was no further increase in the currents, probably due to the establishment of charge generation control under the given light intensity.

3.3.2 | H_2O_2 as Reaction Product and Oxygen Scavenger

The reaction product of oxygen reduction could be H_2O_2 . Small amounts of H_2O_2 have indeed been detected in the photoelectrochemical reduction of oxygen-saturated solutions in contact with p-CuO electrodes [1]. However, the CB of Cu_2O is much more negative, so H_2O_2 as a reaction product, if formed, would be easily reduced, and consequently, no H_2O_2 was detected by chemical analysis after the experiments. In fact, photoelectro-

FIGURE 6 | X-ray diffraction (XRD) before, after long time polarisation under light (0.1 M Na₂SO₄, pH 6, $E = -0.5$ V versus Ag/AgCl, simulated AM1.5 radiation) in oxygen and air saturated solution (with inset of a slow scan XRD). Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS) reference lines from [16, 17].

FIGURE 7 | Influence of H₂O₂ as electron acceptor. Supporting electrolyte 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 6), $E = -0.5$ V versus Ag/AgCl, simulated AM1.5 radiation. Upper trace: O₂ saturated electrolyte and lower trace: N₂ saturated electrolyte, 0.1 M H₂O₂.

chemical reduction of H₂O₂ on Cu₂O on Pt has already been observed [22]. With the present electrodeposited electrodes on FTO, H₂O₂ was used as an electron scavenger (Figure 7). To check whether suppression of reduction of Cu₂O to Cu could be achieved in the absence of stabilization by dissolved oxygen, the solution was purged with N₂ so that no electron acceptor was present except H₂O₂. Figure 7 shows that with 0.1 M H₂O₂, dark currents were enhanced as in the case of oxygen (Figure 5) but were 10 times higher (for a 100 times higher concentration of electroactive species). The photocurrents were about four times higher (compared with the upper trace in Figure 5 where dark and light currents in an O₂-saturated solution are shown).

In the amperometric irradiation experiment, the photoresponse to H₂O₂ did not decrease very much in the course of the long run.

FIGURE 8 | Time course of the current density. Upper curve: oxygen saturated, $E = -0.5$ V versus Ag/AgCl, lower curve: with 0.1 M MV²⁺, oxygen saturated, $E = -0.3$ V versus Ag/AgCl. Supporting electrolyte 0.1 M Na₂SO₄, AM1.5 simulated sunlight.

The dark current doubled when fresh H₂O₂ was added (nominally doubling the initial concentration—see event at $t = 12,500$ s). The photocurrent (current under illumination minus current in the dark) did not change due to H₂O₂ addition. This shows that dark currents were proportional to the H₂O₂ concentration in the studied range, whereas photocurrents were already maximized in 0.1 M H₂O₂, which means that with this concentration all photogenerated carriers were channelled into H₂O₂ reduction instead of auto-reducing Cu₂O. The total charge carried through the electrode (end after 27,000 s reaction time not shown in the graph) was -43 C/cm². The possible reaction during dark and light periods was most probably H₂O₂ reduction to water. There were no traces of Cu found by XRD after this experiment. The exact dependence of dark and photocurrents on the concentration of electron acceptors for Cu₂O electrodes prepared in the above-described way remains to be studied. Electrode response on persulfate as also described [22] could not be reproduced, as the here prepared electrodes were immediately oxidized when exposed to a persulfate-containing electrolyte.

3.3.3 | Methylviologen

As a scavenger for CB electrons also MV is a candidate. It has drawn attention due to the possibility of acting as an electron transfer relay to a suitable catalyst producing hydrogen [23]. The redox potential of the cation ($E^0(\text{MV}^{++}/\text{MV}^{+\cdot}) = -0.45$ V vs. NHE [24]) would allow it to be reduced by photogenerated CB electrons in Cu₂O. However, due to adsorption of the MV⁺ radical [25], dimerization, or further reduction to the insoluble MV⁰ ($E^0(\text{MV}^{+\cdot}/\text{MV}^0) = -1.11$ V vs. NHE [24]), inactivation of the electrode is expected. This was already shown earlier [19, 26], when only air but not oxygen was used in combination with MV.

Figure 8 shows that in oxygen-saturated solutions the photocurrents tripled with 0.1 M MV²⁺ compared to currents in its absence (upper trace in Figure 8. Curve under oxygen at -0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl). However, stabilization with O₂ (reoxidation) was necessary, in order to hinder dimerization or further reduction to MV⁰ and association of the latter to MV⁰_n [24]. As

FIGURE 9 | Photographs of electrodes after prolonged irradiation in MV^{2+} solution (0.1 M MV^{2+}), air saturated, $E = -0.3$ V versus Ag/AgCl. Supporting electrolyte 0.1 M Na_2SO_4 , AM1.5 simulated sunlight. (a) front-side and (b) backside.

MV^{+} can easily be reoxidized with oxygen, no stable product of the photoelectrochemical reaction can be obtained under these conditions.

The photographs (Figure 9) show that when reduced MV was not removed (by reoxidation with oxygen), a whitish layer was deposited originating from reactions of MV^{+} radicals and MV^0 , leading to the monocation dimer MV_2^{+} and finally to the polymer MV_n^0 [24] which blocked the electrode. The backside view in Figure 9b shows the presence of intact parts of the pristine electrode beneath the blocking layer. The corresponding $i-t$ curve for the case of the formation of the blocking layer (Figure 9) is shown in Figure S3. The initial photocathodic current density decreased from ~ 350 to $\sim 90 \mu A/cm^2$ while the dark current density was for the whole polarization time around $80 \mu A/cm^2$.

4 | Conclusions

Electrodeposited Cu_2O films were p-type. In junctions with aqueous electrolytes, cathodic currents passed when reducible redox compounds were added. The electrodes did not block the dark reduction of the added electron acceptors, but the cathodic dark current increased with their concentration. This may be due to interband states and the fact that in the case of p-type electrodes, dark current limitation under reverse bias is not very efficient as local high fields at dislocations and kinks lead to thermal activation of minority carriers. Photocurrents also increased as a function of the concentration of added electron scavengers. The concentration dependence of both, dark- and photocurrents will be addressed in a forthcoming study.

Long-time photoelectrochemical experiments under fixed bias showed that oxygen-saturated and H_2O_2 -containing electrolytes yielded high dark currents and photocurrents. After long-time illumination, no reduction of the electrodes (formation of Cu) was

indicated by XRD when electron scavengers like O_2 or H_2O_2 were offered.

MV was shown to be able to intercept CB electrons: cathodic photocurrents in oxygen-saturated solutions tripled when 0.1 M MV^{2+} was also present. However, stabilization with O_2 (reoxidation of the reduced form) was necessary, in order to hinder dimerization or further reduction to MV^0 and association of the latter to MV_n^0 , the presence of which became evident by the formation of a whitish layer on top of the electrodes.

Author Contributions

Michael Neumann-Spallart: conceptualization, original draft, investigation and writing-review & editing. **Dharini Bhagat:** investigation. **Šárka Paušová:** investigation, data curation and writing-review & editing. **Josef Krýsa:** Funding acquisition, conceptualization and writing-review & editing. **Indrajit Mukhopadhyay:** Conceptualization.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the project “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by the Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call “Excellent Research”.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data are available at <https://zenodo.org/records/12531583>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.